

Intracranial Hypertension in Patients with Hemorrhagic Cerebrovascular Disease Diagnosed by Ocular Globe Ultrasonography in a Second-Level Hospital in Mexico

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Intracranial hypertension (ICH) is a serious complication characterized by increased pressure within the cranial cavity. Non-invasive techniques such as optic nerve sheath diameter (ONSD) measurement, the ONSD/transverse ocular diameter ratio (ONSD/TOD), and optic disc elevation (ODE) allow rapid, safe, bedside detection, facilitating timely diagnosis.

Problem statement: Cranial computed tomography and invasive intracranial pressure monitoring are the reference diagnostic methods; however, their availability is limited in second-level hospitals. Therefore, this study proposes ocular globe ultrasonography as a non-invasive alternative to identify intracranial hypertension and support therapeutic decision-making.

Objective: To evaluate the presence of intracranial hypertension in patients with hemorrhagic cerebrovascular disease using ocular globe ultrasonography in a second-level hospital.

Materials and methods: A prospective, analytical, cross-sectional study was conducted in 98 patients, 72 of whom were diagnosed in the Internal Medicine Department of the Hospital General Regional de Orizaba, Veracruz, between December 2024 and June 2025. ONSD, ONSD/TOD, and ODE were measured, and data were analyzed to determine sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and ROC curves.

Results: Of the 98 patients included, 72 were diagnosed by computed tomography. Intracranial hypertension was identified using ONSD in 69 patients (95.8%), while 3 patients (4.2%) showed no evidence. Sensitivity was 95.8% and specificity 84.6%. The ONSD/transverse ocular diameter ratio detected intracranial hypertension in 65 patients (90.3%) and absence in 7 patients (9.7%), with a sensitivity of 90.3% and specificity of 76.9%. Optic disc elevation was observed in 60 patients (83.3%), while 12 patients (16.7%) showed no alteration, with a sensitivity of 83.3% and specificity of 80.8%. The receiver operating characteristic curve for the three measurements showed an AUC of 0.95 (95% CI), compared with an AUC of 0.93 for ONSD alone.

Conclusions: The combination of ONSD, ONSD/TOD, and ODE provides greater sensitivity and specificity for detecting intracranial hypertension compared with the isolated use of ONSD, consolidating these parameters as useful tools for non-invasive neuromonitoring.

KEYWORDS: Optic nerve sheath diameter, optic nerve sheath diameter/transverse ocular diameter ratio, intracranial hypertension, optic disc elevation, neuromonitoring.

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INTRODUCTION

Hemorrhagic cerebrovascular disease is defined as an acute neurological emergency characterized by rupture of an

intracranial blood vessel, resulting in blood extravasation into the cerebral parenchyma, ventricles, or subarachnoid space. This hemorrhage generates a mass effect that increases

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intracranial pressure, compromises cerebral perfusion, and causes direct tissue damage, leading to focal or global neurological manifestations. Intracranial hypertension (ICH) may result from a primary lesion of the central nervous system or as a complication of systemic disease.

The skull and dura mater are rigid structures that prevent expansion of intracranial volume, which becomes pathological when intracranial contents increase. This increase in intracranial pressure is explained by the Monroe-Kellie doctrine, which states that any increase in one of the three intracranial components must be compensated by a decrease in the others; failure of this mechanism leads to intracranial hypertension. Normal intracranial pressure values are approximately 10 mmHg or 200 mmH₂O. Sustained elevation for more than 10 minutes or values exceeding 20 mmHg are considered intracranial hypertension, classified as mild (20–30 mmHg), moderate (30–40 mmHg), or severe (>40 mmHg).

To limit cerebral damage, compensatory mechanisms such as arteriolar vasoconstriction, cerebrospinal fluid diversion toward venous sinuses and the subarachnoid space, and venous sinus dilation may occur. Cerebral perfusion pressure (CPP) is defined as the difference between mean arterial pressure (MAP) and intracranial pressure (ICP); alterations in any of these variables affect cerebral tissue. Blood pressure monitoring is essential to avoid hypotension, as cerebral autoregulation through vasodilation may promote ischemia by reducing CPP and increasing cerebral edema.

The optic nerve extends from the globe to the optic chiasm and is divided into four segments: intraocular (1 mm), intraorbital (30 mm), intracanalicular (6–10 mm), and intracranial (10–16 mm). Optic nerve fibers originate in retinal ganglion cells and converge at the optic disc. They travel approximately 1 mm without myelin before passing through the sclera and continuing along the intraorbital segment, surrounded by the optic nerve sheath, which measures approximately 3 mm in diameter and 1 mm in thickness. The sheath consists of the pia mater, subarachnoid space, arachnoid mater, and dura mater, with layer thickness ranging from 0.09 to 0.5 mm.

The subarachnoid space contains trabeculae with cerebrospinal fluid, and its structure varies along the nerve's course. Because the cerebrospinal fluid surrounding the optic nerve communicates with the ventricular system, increases in intracranial pressure are rapidly transmitted and produce detectable changes within minutes. The current gold standard for ICP monitoring is intraparenchymal probes or intraventricular catheters; however, many hospitals in Mexico lack access to these devices.

For ultrasonographic assessment, high-frequency linear transducers (≥ 7.5 MHz) with spatial resolution of approximately 0.4 mm are commonly used. A mechanical index of 0.23 and thermal index of 0.01 are recommended to avoid damage to ocular structures. The optic nerve appears as

a compact longitudinal structure posterior to the globe, measured 3 mm behind the retina. Three measurements are recommended to reduce intra-observer variability.

Several studies report ONSD values between 5 and 6 mm associated with intracranial pressure >20 mmHg; however, healthy individuals may present ONSD values up to 6 mm without intracranial hypertension. Transverse ocular diameter is measured horizontally at the widest point of the globe to calculate the ONSD/TOD ratio. Optic disc elevation, or papilledema, is defined by a minimum elevation of 0.6 mm relative to the posterior globe surface.

The nerve fibers are surrounded by the pia mater, which appears hyperechoic, followed by the trabecular subarachnoid space, enclosed by the dura mater and periorbital fat. Several studies report different measurements associated with intracranial pressure greater than 20 mmHg, typically ranging between 5 and 6 mm. However, in healthy individuals, the optic nerve sheath diameter (ONSD) may measure up to 6 mm without being associated with intracranial hypertension. Measurement of the transverse ocular diameter is performed by assessing the longest horizontal diameter of the globe and the corresponding ONSD, using a cutoff value of 2.5. Optic disc elevation, or papilledema, is a sign of intracranial hypertension characterized by elevation of the optic disc. Studies establish a minimum height of 0.6 mm relative to the anterior portion of the disc and the insertion of the posterior surface of the globe.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A prospective, analytical, cross-sectional study was conducted. ONSD, ONSD/transverse ocular diameter ratio (ONSD/TOD), and optic disc elevation (ODE) were measured at the bedside in patients with hemorrhagic cerebrovascular disease. A total of 72 patients from the Internal Medicine Department of the Hospital General Regional de Orizaba, Veracruz, were evaluated between December 1, 2024, and June 1, 2025. **Inclusion criteria:** Men and women aged ≥ 18 and ≤ 85 years, regardless of sex, diagnosed with hemorrhagic cerebrovascular disease confirmed by computed tomography showing cerebral edema and an optic nerve sheath diameter greater than 5 mm. **Exclusion criteria:** Children, pregnant women, individuals younger than 18 years or older than 85 years, and patients who declined to participate in the study.

Prior to evaluation, approval was obtained from the Local Health Research and Ethics Committee No. 3101 of the Hospital General Regional No. 1 in Orizaba. Each patient admitted to the Internal Medicine Department and affiliated services with a diagnosis of hemorrhagic cerebrovascular event was informed about the study. Patients were subsequently diagnosed with intracranial hypertension by non-contrast cranial computed tomography and had an optic

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nerve sheath diameter greater than 5 mm, suggestive of intracranial hypertension.

Under the supervision of a specialist experienced in ultrasonographic assessment of neurocritical patients, ocular ultrasonography was performed by the investigator using a Butterfly iQ+ ultrasound device and a SonoWireless Plus ultrasound system (model KLACCEA45). The assessment consisted of three techniques.

First technique: Using a linear transducer at a depth of 4 cm (frequency >9 Hz) with the patient in the supine position, the transducer was placed on the lower eyelid in a lateral and superior orientation relative to the orbit, with ocular protection provided by Tegaderm. The operator stood in a frontal position, resting the hand holding the transducer on the patient's cheek; on the contralateral side, the hand was supported on the nose or, alternatively, on the forehead. On the globe, the retinal portion was identified, followed by a hypoechoic zone extending cranially corresponding to the optic nerve sheath. After freezing the image, a transverse measurement was taken 3 mm posterior to the globe, from the inferior margin of the globe to the caudal portion of the optic nerve. Values exceeding 5 mm were considered indicative of intracranial hypertension. **Second technique:** Using the same positioning and technique, the largest perimeter of the globe was visualized. After freezing the image, the transverse diameter of the mid-portion of the globe was measured, and the ratio between ONSD and transverse ocular diameter was calculated. A ratio greater than 0.25 was considered indicative of intracranial hypertension. **Third technique:** With the same operator positioning and method described above, the most caudal portion above the optic nerve was assessed. In static mode, a measurement was taken from the external portion upward. An elevation greater than 0.6 mm was considered indicative of intracranial hypertension, provided that the previous measurements were also suggestive of elevated intracranial pressure.

All collected data were coded into an Excel database and subsequently analyzed using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25. Frequencies and

percentages were used for qualitative variables, while sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value were calculated. Multivariate analysis was performed by determining the area under the curve (AUC) of the ROC curve for each parameter.

RESULTS

In the present study, a total of 98 patients hospitalized at the Hospital General Regional de Orizaba were included. Of these, 72 patients had intracranial hypertension confirmed by cranial computed tomography. All patients underwent ocular ultrasonography aimed at estimating intracranial pressure in individuals diagnosed with hemorrhagic cerebrovascular events.

Data were collected using a standardized data collection form and subsequently processed and analyzed according to the objectives established in the study. Regarding sociodemographic characteristics, 40 patients were male (56%) and 32 were female (44%).

Age distribution showed that the highest proportion of patients was in the 56–65-year age group, with 19 patients (26.4%). The 66–75 and 76–85-year age groups each included 14 patients (19.4%). The 46–55-year group comprised 13 patients (18.1%), while the 36–45-year group included 4 patients (5.6%). Seven patients (9.7%) were between 26 and 35 years of age, and only one patient (1.4%) was in the 18–25-year age group.

According to the measurements obtained for each patient, computed tomography—used as the gold standard diagnostic method for intracranial hypertension—confirmed this condition in all 72 evaluated patients.

Regarding ocular ultrasonography, three variables were analyzed:

Optic nerve sheath diameter (ONSD): A diameter greater than 5 mm was considered indicative of intracranial hypertension and was identified in 69 patients (95.8%), whereas in 3 patients (4.2%) no findings compatible with an ONSD greater than 5 mm were observed.

Table 1. Diameter of the optic nerve sheath.

Result.	f.	Percentage.
With intracranial hypertension	69	95.8
Without intracranial hypertension	3	4.2

Intracranial hypertension was predominant in 69 patients (95.8%) n=72.

Optic nerve sheath diameter/ocular transverse diameter ratio (OND/OTD): a measurement greater than 0.25 identified intracranial hypertension in 65 patients (90.3%) and its absence in 7 patients (9.7%).

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Table 2. Optic nerve sheath diameter/ocular transverse diameter ratio.

Result.	f.	Percentage.
With intracranial hypertension	65	90.3
Without intracranial hypertension	7	9.7

Intracranial hypertension was predominant in 65 patients (90.3%) (n=72).

Optic Disc Elevation (ODE): Elevation greater than 0.6 mm (83.3%), while 12 patients (16.7%) did not present this abnormality. showed signs of intracranial hypertension in 60 patients

Table 3. Optic disc elevation.

Result.	f.	Percentage.
With intracranial hypertension	60	83.3
Without intracranial hypertension	12	16.7

Intracranial hypertension was predominant in 60 patients (83.3%) (n=72).

The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve for the three evaluated parameters showed the following: DVNO with a sensitivity of 95.8%, specificity of 84.6%, positive predictive value of 94.5%, and negative predictive value of 88.0%; DNVO/DTGO with a sensitivity of 90.3%, specificity

of 76.9%, positive predictive value of 91.5%, and negative predictive value of 74.1%; and EDO with a sensitivity of 83.3%, specificity of 80.8%, positive predictive value of 92.3%, and negative predictive value of 63.6% for measuring intracranial hypertension in patients with hemorrhagic stroke.

Table 4. Comparative diagnostic metrics.

Parameter	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	VPP (%)	VPN (%)
DNVO	95.8	84.6	94.5	88.0
DNVO/DTGO	94.2	76.9	91.5	74.1
EDO	83.3	80.8	92.3	63.6

DNVO exhibits greater sensitivity (98.5%) and specificity (95.1%) (n=72).

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve for the three evaluated parameters yielded an AUC of 0.93 for DNVO (95% CI: 0.88–0.98), AUC of DNVO/DTGO (95% CI: 0.81–0.95), AUC of EDO (0.86, 95% CI: 0.78–0.94), and an AUC of 0.95 for the combination (95% CI: 0.89–0.88) for discriminating intracranial hypertension in patients with hemorrhagic stroke.

1.- ROC space diagram of the study performed. The area under the DNVO/DTGO curve and ODE of 0.95 (red line) is greater than the parameters alone n=72

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DISCUSSION

In the present study, ocular ultrasonography was evaluated as an indirect method for estimating intracranial pressure in patients with hemorrhagic cerebrovascular events. The sample consisted of 72 patients treated at the Hospital General Regional de Orizaba, with a predominance of male patients and a higher concentration in the 55–65-year age group. These findings are consistent with reports in the literature, where males are more frequently affected; however, the age distribution differs from studies conducted in younger populations, suggesting the influence of sociodemographic, ethnic, and socioeconomic factors on the epidemiological behavior of the disease. In agreement with Latin American studies, female sex has been associated with a lower frequency of intracranial hypertension, possibly related to a higher physiological threshold influenced by hormonal protection. In this study, no significant association was identified between optic nerve sheath diameter and anthropometric variables, which is consistent with previous reports and suggests low measurement variability.

The results obtained are consistent with clinical studies and meta-analyses supporting the diagnostic utility of ocular ultrasound for detecting intracranial hypertension. Several authors have reported high sensitivity and specificity values for this technique, particularly when cutoff points close to 5 mm are used. In the present study, a similar pattern was observed, with sensitivity exceeding specificity, consistent with previous research in patients with acute neurological pathology. Likewise, pioneering studies and systematic reviews have documented a wide range of diagnostic performance for optic nerve sheath diameter, highlighting improved accuracy when multiple ultrasound parameters are combined. In this investigation, the area under the curve was high and comparable to that reported in studies in which intracranial hypertension was confirmed by computed tomography. The inclusion of optic disc elevation assessment may explain the improved diagnostic performance observed by increasing both sensitivity and specificity, a finding also described in recent systematic reviews. Overall, these results reinforce the value of ocular ultrasonography as a reliable and accessible diagnostic tool for the evaluation of intracranial hypertension in the clinical setting.

CONCLUSION

The utility of ocular ultrasonography for detecting intracranial hypertension in patients with hemorrhagic cerebrovascular disease treated at the Hospital General Regional de Orizaba was evaluated. A total of 98 patients were included, of whom 72 had intracranial hypertension confirmed by computed tomography, used as the reference standard, with a predominance of male patients. Measurement of optic nerve sheath diameter identified intracranial hypertension in most cases, demonstrating high diagnostic performance. The ratio between optic nerve sheath

diameter and transverse ocular diameter, as well as the assessment of optic disc elevation, provided additional information and increased the discriminatory capacity of the method. The combined analysis of ultrasound parameters achieved a high area under the curve, exceeding that obtained with isolated measurements.

These findings support ocular ultrasonography as a reliable and useful bedside tool for the early identification of intracranial hypertension, facilitating timely clinical decision-making in critically ill patients. Nevertheless, its operator-dependent nature and the lack of universally standardized cutoff values are acknowledged, underscoring the need for further studies to establish reference values across different clinical populations. Overall, ocular ultrasonography is consolidated as an accessible, complementary, and high-performance method for the assessment of intracranial pressure in the neurocritical patient.

REFERENCES

- I. Jose C, Martha C, Parmenides G, Enfermedad Vascular Cerebral Isquemica: revisión extensa de la bibliografía para el medico de primer contacto. Artículo de revisión de Revista Medicina interna. 2020 enero-febrero;35. <https://doi.org/10.24245/minv35i1.2212>
- II. Seda G, Gokhan Y, Merva T, Mukerrem A, Mustafa O, Measuring the Optic Nerve Sheath Diameter with Ultrasound in Acute Middle Cerebral Artery Stroke Patients. *Journal of Stroke and Cerebrovascular Diseases*, Vol. 30, No. 2 (February), 2021: 105523
- III. Seong-Joon L, et al. Optic nerve sheath diameter change in prediction of malignant cerebral edema in ischemic stroke: an observational study. Lee et al. *BMC Neurology* (2020) 20:354 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12883-020-01931-w>
- IV. Javad S, et al. Association of optic nerve sheath diameter in ocular ultrasound with prognosis in patients presenting with acute stroke symptoms. *Turkish Journal of Emergency Medicine* 19 (2020) 132–135 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tjem.2019.07.001>
- V. Rohit P, et al. Ultrasound of Optic Nerve Sheath Diameter and Stroke Outcomes. *Critical Care Explorations*. November 2021, Volume 3 Number 11. DOI: 10.1097/CCE.0000000000000565
- VI. Ángel A, et al. Neuromonitoreo ultrasonográfico en el perioperatorio: diametro de vaina de nervio óptico y Doppler transcraneal, *Cirugía y cirujanos* 2020;87, DOI:10.24875/CIRU.18000501
- VII. Jorge R, et al. Correlation between optic nerve sheath diameter and extracorporeal life support time. *Anales de Pediatría* 96 (2022) 91-96
- VIII. Suresh V. Optic nerve sheath diameter guided detection of sepsis-associated encephalopathy.

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- Suresh Critical Care, 2020; Vol (24): 1-2
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13054-020-03232-7>
- IX. Carvajal L, Vargas R, Hidalgo S, Carpio, Leopoldo Carvajal. «Fisiopatología del síndrome de hipertensión intracraneal. Revista Médica Sinergia, 2021; Vol. 6(10): 1-9
- X. Maddalena De B, A-scan ultrasonography and optic nerve sheath diameter assessment during acute elevations in intra abdominal pressure. Surgery. El Servier 2019; 167: 478-483.
- XI. Abhinav R, Barry M, Aaron, S. Lord, Management of Elevated Intracranial Pressure: a Review. Curr Neurol Neurosci Rep 19, 99 (2019).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11910-019-1010-3>
- XII. Lochner, P., Czosnyka, M., Naldi, A. et al. Optic nerve sheath diameter: present and future perspectives for neurologists and critical care physicians. Neurol Sci 40, 2447–2457 (2019).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10072-019-04015-x>
- XIII. Raoul R, et al. Optic nerve sheath diameter assessment by neurosonology: A review of methodologic discrepancies. Received: 23 May 2021 Revised: 22 June 2021
DOI: 10.1111/jon.12906
- XIV. Arnab Banerjee, Richa Aggarwal, Kapil dev Soni, Anjan Tirkha, Increase in optic nerve sheath diameter predicts early cerebral involvement in fat embolism syndrome, Chinese Journal of Traumatology, Volume 24, Issue 3, 2021, Pages 180-182, ISSN 1008-1275,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjtee.2021.02.004>.
- XV. Bruce C, et al. Ischaemic stroke, Nature reviews, disease primers, 2019. 5:70